

APPLICATIONS OF COMPOSITE TECHNOLOGIES TO AEROSPACE SYSTEMS IN KARI

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1 Introduction to KARI

Having launched our first satellite in 1992, the history of space development in Korea is quite short compared with the major space faring countries. In spite of this short history, with the strong support of the Korean government, much has been accomplished during this short period with 15 satellites (including commercial satellites) in orbit, 3 successfully launched sounding rockets, and the recent successful launch of the Naro space launch vehicle (KSLV-1).

The Korea Aerospace Research Institute, established in 1989, has played a key role in implementing national space programs through research and development of aerospace technology with its mission to contribute to the development of the national economy and improvement of the quality of life for the Korean people through aerospace technology research & development.

In the field of satellite technology, KARI developed the Korea Multipurpose Satellites (KOMPSAT-1, 2, 3) and the Communications, Oceanography and Meteorology Satellite (COMS). In the field of launch vehicle technology, KARI established the Naro Space Center in 2009 and successfully completed the KSLV-1 project by launching a 100kg class small satellite (STSAT-2) into a low-earth orbit on Jan. 30 this year. In the aeronautics field, KARI participated in the Korea Helicopter Project as well as the Smart Unmanned Air Vehicle Project.

Current programs at KARI include the KOMPSAT-5, KOMPSAT-3A, and STSAT-3 satellite programs and the KSLV-II launch vehicle program.

2 Applications of composite materials to the aerospace systems in KARI

A robust and intelligent tilt rotor UAV (Fig. 1) exhibiting high-speed cruise and VTOL capabilities

has been developed by KARI since 2002. This is designed to take-off and land vertically, and cruise like an airplane using a tilting rotor mechanism which is located at the wing tips. Most of the structures except for joint fittings and some bulkheads were made of composite materials to have light weight and low cost. The top design requirements of Smart UAV are 5 hours of flight time, a speed of 500 km/hr, and a 1000 kg takeoff weight with a 40 kg payload. A carbon fiber reinforced BMI matrix using resin transfer moulding process is applied for high temperature zones around engine exhaust ducts. In the results of the full scale static test, it was shown that the structures of Smart UAV can hold up to 165 % of the design load.

Naro-1, previously designated Korea Space Launch Vehicle or KSLV, is Korea's first carrier rocket, and the first Korean launch vehicle to achieve Earth orbit. Application of composite materials in the upper stage of the launch vehicle includes PLF (Payload Fairing), kick motor case, nozzle, equipment bay structure, and RCS (Reaction Control System) tank (Fig. 2). The kick motor case is filament wound using high-strength carbon fiber and epoxy resin. It is about 1 m in diameter and 1.7 m in length. The kick motor nozzle consists of 4D Carbon/Carbon, Sillica/Phenolic, Carbon/Phenolic and Glass/Phenolic to withstand the firing condition of about 3000°C and high pressure. The equipment bay and panels designed to carry and support the main equipments are sandwich structures fabricated with carbon/epoxy facet sheet and honeycomb core. Different core material such as aluminum and Nomex are used for the strength and stiffness requirements. The RCS tank is made of aluminum seamless liner and composite overwrapping with carbon fiber and epoxy by filament winding process. In recent years, the trends of spacecraft design have been towards smaller and lighter satellites. To

reduce the volume and weight of the satellite, the MFS (Multi-Functional Structure) concept as a new system for spacecraft design that folds the electronics into the walls of the spacecraft has been developed. The MFS integrates the electronics, thermal control and structure into a single packaging system, so, it can eliminate the chassis/frames, PWBs (Printed-Wiring Boards), cables and connectors of the electronic boxes. The rectangular grid-stiffened structure (Fig. 3), which is made of the skin and ribs, is designed and manufactured using the pan-based CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics). The pitch-based CFRP is bonded on the skin of the pan-based CFRP of the exterior of the structure to promote better heat transfer.

3 Development of HSTS(High Stability Telescope Structures) for EO(Electro-Optical) cameras

The composite technology required for the HSTS to obtain stable high resolution satellite images in the extreme space environment is very important for the satellite EO camera system. KARI KOMPSAT satellites are orbiting in SSO (Sun Synchronous Orbit) at about 685 Km. The large size mirror of the camera system and the supporting structure should be stable thermally under extreme conditions such as high temperatures in the sunlight, almost zero absolute temperature in the shade and the resulting high temperature gradient. Any appreciable distortions due to thermal deformation in space would result the serious deterioration of the camera resolution resulting in blurred images. However, the camera system should be light weight and strong enough to withstand the severe blasting loads in the rocket launch event. Composite material may be considered as one of the best candidates for the HSTS if the appropriate engineering is applied. In KOMPSAT2, the hand-layup technology of prepreg for the 0.75m dia. and 1.3m long camera was used and thermal deformation under $2 \mu\text{m}$ ($\Delta T = 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{K}$) was achieved. In KOMPSAT3, the Filament Winding technology by using M60J as fiber and L20SL Epoxy for the 0.93m dia. and 2.1m long camera and the thermal deformation under $3 \mu\text{m}$ ($\Delta T = 4 \text{ }^\circ\text{K}$) was observed. For the next EO satellite, we are now developing a camera of less than 0.5m EO resolution with hand-layup(Fig. 4).

4 Summary

Composite technologies have provided a lot of solutions for aerospace systems like aircrafts, satellites and rockets for KARI seeking light weight and extreme temperature and load endurance. Particularly, the successful development of the HSTS proved that the CFRP technology is well suited for such large and highly dimensionally stable structures for optical instruments. Furthermore, the achieved results indicate clearly that the potential is given for even larger sized optical telescope structures.

Fig. 1. Robust and intelligent tilt rotor UAV

Fig. 2. Upper stage of the launch vehicle, NARO

Fig. 3. Rectangular grid-stiffened structure for KOMPSAT programs

Fig. 4. HSTS for 0.5m EO resolution(1.2m dia. and 1.9m long) under 3-D measurement